

Solvent hydrogen bonding and structural effects on nucleophilic aromatic substitution reactions. Part-2 : Reaction of benzenesulphonyl chloride with anilines in propan-2-ol/2-methylpropan-2-ol mixtures[†]

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Manuscript received 16 April 2008, revised 15 October 2008, accepted 27 October 2008

Abstract : Substitution reactions of fourteen *para*- and *meta*-substituted anilines with benzenesulphonyl chloride in different mole fractions of propan-2-ol in 2-methylpropan-2-ol have been investigated conductometrically. The second order rate constants correlates satisfactorily with pK_a values of the anilines and also with the Hammett's substituent constant. The *para*-substituted anilines shows a satisfactory correlation with Charton's LDR equation. The results of these correlations indicate the formation of an electron deficient transition state. The rate data correlate satisfactorily with macroscopic solvent parameters such as relative permittivity, ϵ_r and polarity, E_T^N . Multiple correlation analysis of the rate data via Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic parameters reveals that the solvent dipolarity/polarizability plays a dominant role in governing the reactivity.

Keywords : Aniline, benzenesulphonyl chloride, substitution reaction, solvent effect.

Introduction

The study of solute-solvent interactions in binary mixtures is more complex than in pure solvents. In a pure solvent the composition of the microsphere of solvation of a solute, the so called cybotatic region, is the same as in the bulk solvent, but in binary mixtures the composition in this microsphere can be different. The solute can interact to a different degree with the components of the mixture, and this difference in the interactions is reflected in the composition of the microsphere of solvation. The effect of varying the composition of the mixture from the bulk solvent to the solvation sphere is called preferential solvation².

The literature lacks in the study of effect of solvent hydrogen bonding on S_NAr reactions. Remarkable among these attempts is the study of the effects of added hydrogen-bond donor and hydrogen-bond acceptor co-solvents on such reactions¹⁻⁷. Having successfully studied and rationalized sometimes conflicting effects of hydrogen bonding of the co-solvent on S_NAr reactions, we find it necessary to have a more general view of the phenomenon. Keeping this in view, a systematic study of various Linear Free Energy Relationships has been made to establish

the role of solvent and substituents on reactivity and to decide the nature of the mechanism followed in the reaction of several *meta*- and *para*-substituted anilines with benzenesulphonyl chloride in propan-2-ol/2-methylpropan-2-ol mixtures of varying compositions. This mixture is so chosen that by varying the mole fraction of the constituent solvents, the hydrogen bonding properties of the medium can be varied in a smooth and continuous manner. Though propan-2-ol has polarity and hydrogen bond acceptor capabilities similar to those of 2-methylpropan-2-ol, it has strong hydrogen bond donor property⁸. The present work is, to the best of our knowledge, the first systematic kinetic study in this solvent mixture.

Experimental

Materials : All the chemicals (Aldrich or Merck, India) used were of analytical grade. The solvents 2-methylpropan-2-ol and propan-2-ol were of chromatographic grade and used as received. The solid anilines were used as such and the liquid anilines were used after vacuum distillation.

Kinetic studies : The reactions of benzenesulphonyl chloride with substituted anilines in varying mole frac-

[†]For Part-1, Ref. 1.

tions of propan-2-ol in 2-methylpropan-2-ol were followed conductometrically at 30, 40 and 50 \pm 0.1 $^{\circ}$ C. The concentration of benzenesulphonyl chloride was 5×10^{-4} M and that of aniline was between 0.01 to 0.02 M. Pseudo-first order conditions were used in all cases. Regression coefficients of all the reaction rate constants were around 0.97. The reaction is so slow that it is inconvenient to wait for its completion. Therefore, the Guggenheim method⁹ was used to evaluate the rate constants by carrying out the kinetic runs for up to 3 h. The second order rate constants, k_2 , were obtained from the observed rate constants as reported earlier⁷. All rate determinations were carried out at least in duplicate and the rate constants are accurate to within $\pm 2\%$.

Data analysis : Correlation analyses were carried out using Microcal Origin (version 6) computer software. The goodness of the fit was discussed using correlation coefficient and standard deviation, σ^{10} . The percentage contribution (P_x) of a parameter to the total effect on reactivity was computed using the regression coefficient of each parameter as reported earlier¹¹.

Results and discussion

The nucleophilic substitution reaction of aniline and *para*-(Me, OMe, COMe, NHCOMe, NO₂, Br, Cl, F) and *meta*-(Me, OMe, COMe, Et, NO₂) substituted anilines were studied conductometrically at three different temperatures in presence of varying excess of the aniline over the substrate to ensure pseudo-first order kinetics. The second order rate constants, k_2 , computed and are summarized in Table 1. The reactions were carried out in varying mole fractions of propan-2-ol in 2-methylpropan-2-ol. The selection of the mole fractions was based on the fact that the solvatochromic parameters employed in the present study for correlation analysis are available in the literature². The overall reaction is represented as follows.

Survey of literature shows that the generally accepted mechanism of S_NAr reactions of anilines with benzenesulphonyl chlorides¹² and other aromatic sulphonyl

chlorides¹³ is well established and involves a transition state (I) as given below.

The results in Table 1 reveal that increase in mole fraction of propan-2-ol in the mixture increases the rate of the reaction.

Activation parameters and the isokinetic relationship : The activation parameters were calculated from k_2 at 303, 313 and 323 K using the van't Hoff plot by the method of least squares and are collected in Table 2. The operation of isokinetic relationship is tested by plotting the logarithms of rate constants at two temperatures ($T_2 > T_1$) against each other according to eq. (1) as suggested by Exner¹⁴.

$$\log k \text{ (at } T_2) = a + b \log k \text{ (at } T_1) \quad (1)$$

In the present study linear plots imply the validity of isokinetic relationship. A representative plot is shown in Fig. 1 (in 0.5572 mole fraction of propan-2-ol, $r = 0.987$,

Fig. 1. The isokinetic plot for all the anilines in 0.5572 mole fraction.

Table 1. Second order rate constants ($10^4 k_2$, s^{-1}) for the substitution of anilines in varying mole fraction of propan-2-ol in 2-methylpropan-2-ol

Substituents in aniline	Mole fraction of propan-2-ol												
	1.0000	0.9598	0.8770	0.7003	0.5572	0.4545	0.3490	0.1995	0.1485	0.1108	0.0696	0.0475	0.0243
moiety	32.40	30.63	25.87	21.18	18.16	16.81	16.44	16.07	15.69	15.32	14.95	14.58	14.20
H	47.47	34.83	23.01	22.18	21.83	21.53	20.56	20.28	19.86	19.14	18.84	18.53	17.70
<i>p</i> -Me	52.99	42.98	36.47	22.96	24.77	23.33	27.16	25.06	22.33	20.04	17.58	14.99	15.74
<i>p</i> -OMe	14.30	14.09	13.60	13.18	12.90	12.56	11.95	11.12	10.69	10.10	9.74	9.28	8.90
<i>p</i> -COMe	32.80	25.53	18.07	16.25	15.92	15.70	15.45	15.13	14.99	14.86	14.19	14.06	13.83
<i>p</i> -NHCOMe	13.84	13.12	12.40	11.68	10.96	10.24	9.52	8.80	8.08	7.36	6.64	5.92	5.20
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	18.40	17.85	19.40	19.01	17.74	17.18	15.92	15.31	14.06	13.46	12.19	11.61	10.35
<i>p</i> -Cl	18.36	18.23	18.18	17.89	17.34	16.80	15.88	14.69	13.83	12.67	11.28	10.49	9.10
<i>p</i> -Br	28.21	24.46	20.35	19.18	19.02	18.04	17.03	16.08	15.63	14.78	13.25	12.18	11.21
<i>p</i> -F	38.96	26.13	27.23	25.11	21.53	20.51	18.11	19.54	17.62	15.74	13.83	11.91	13.49
<i>m</i> -Me	22.01	21.79	17.10	16.48	15.67	15.27	15.13	14.52	14.32	14.26	14.16	14.09	14.03
<i>m</i> -OMe	14.31	13.96	17.42	15.56	15.52	18.15	16.11	14.06	12.05	9.95	10.71	8.91	7.69
<i>m</i> -COMe	47.43	30.97	19.81	19.50	19.32	18.92	18.36	18.11	17.74	17.34	16.94	16.56	16.18
<i>m</i> -Et	14.18	13.98	11.61	11.51	11.40	11.35	10.86	10.45	10.00	9.57	9.12	8.67	8.22
<i>m</i> -NO ₂													

Table 2. Effect of temperature on the rate of substitution reaction of anilines by benzenesulphonyl chloride in 0.5572 mole fraction of propan-2-ol and activation parameters for the reaction

Substituents in aniline	Rate constants			E_a	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger
	303	313	323 K				
H	18.16	19.27	25.67	14 ± 0.7	12 ± 5	-259 ± 75	90.3
<i>p</i> -Me	21.83	25.80	30.33	14 ± 0.2	11 ± 0.1	-259 ± 1	89.7
<i>p</i> -OMe	24.77	30.36	35.36	15 ± 1	12 ± 1	-254 ± 17	89.4
<i>p</i> -COMe	12.90	13.95	16.28	10 ± 2	7 ± 2	-277 ± 21	91.1
<i>p</i> -NHCOMe	15.92	17.53	22.95	15 ± 4	13 ± 4	-257 ± 58	90.6
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	10.92	12.60	16.42	17 ± 3	14 ± 3	-255 ± 42	91.5
<i>p</i> -Cl	17.74	20.64	23.12	11 ± 1	8 ± 0.8	-270 ± 10	90.2
<i>p</i> -Br	17.34	20.52	23.76	13 ± 0.5	10 ± 0.5	-263 ± 6	90.3
<i>p</i> -F	19.02	22.20	26.95	15 ± 1	12 ± 1	-258 ± 12	90.1
<i>m</i> -Me	21.53	24.26	28.60	12 ± 1	9 ± 1	-266 ± 14	89.8
<i>m</i> -OMe	15.67	17.68	20.68	12 ± 0.8	9 ± 1	-269 ± 10	90.6
<i>m</i> -COMe	15.52	17.23	24.56	19 ± 6	16 ± 5	-245 ± 99	90.7
<i>m</i> -Et	19.32	21.15	24.15	9 ± 1	6 ± 1	-275 ± 11	90.0
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	11.40	13.59	18.58	20 ± 3	18 ± 3	-243 ± 55	91.4

E_a in kJ mol⁻¹ K⁻¹; ΔH^\ddagger in kJ mol⁻¹; ΔS^\ddagger in J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹; ΔG^\ddagger in kJ mol⁻¹.

$\sigma = 0.02$, isokinetic temperature = 160 ± 8 K). The operation of isokinetic relationship reveals that all the substituted anilines examined follow a single mechanism.

The activation energies and the entropies and enthal-

pies of activation were also calculated for the reaction in thirteen different mole fractions of propan-2-ol (Table 3). Negative entropy of activation indicates a greater degree of ordering in the transition state than in the initial

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters and rate constants ($10^4 k_2$ s⁻¹) for the substitution of aniline by benzenesulphonyl chloride in various mole fraction of propan-2-ol in 2-methylpropan-2-ol

Mole fraction of propan-2-ol	Rate constants			E_a	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger	ΔG^\ddagger
	303	313	323 K				
1.0000	32.40	38.97	45.42	14 ± 0.7	11 ± 0.7	-255 ± 10	88.7
0.9598	30.63	35.27	40.23	11 ± 0.2	9 ± 0.2	-264 ± 3	88.9
0.8770	25.87	31.57	37.37	15 ± 0.6	13 ± 0.8	-252 ± 11	89.3
0.7003	21.18	25.42	29.70	14 ± 0.6	11 ± 0.6	-258 ± 8	89.8
0.5572	18.16	19.27	25.67	14 ± 0.7	12 ± 0.6	-259 ± 8	90.3
0.4545	16.81	17.27	23.75	14 ± 0.6	12 ± 0.7	-260 ± 10	90.5
0.3490	16.44	17.20	23.16	14 ± 0.7	12 ± 0.6	-260 ± 8	90.5
0.1995	16.07	17.00	22.70	14 ± 0.8	12 ± 0.7	-260 ± 9	90.6
0.1485	15.69	16.19	21.20	12 ± 0.5	10 ± 0.6	-266 ± 7	90.6
0.1108	15.32	15.39	20.67	12 ± 0.5	10 ± 0.5	-267 ± 7	90.7
0.0696	14.95	15.07	20.16	12 ± 0.5	10 ± 0.6	-267 ± 7	90.8
0.0475	14.58	14.75	19.70	13 ± 0.5	10 ± 0.6	-267 ± 7	90.8
0.0243	14.20	14.43	19.67	14 ± 0.7	11 ± 0.5	-264 ± 7	90.9

E_a in kJ mol⁻¹ K⁻¹; ΔH^\ddagger in kJ mol⁻¹; ΔS^\ddagger in J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹; ΔG^\ddagger in kJ mol⁻¹.

state, due to an increase in solvation during the activation process. The existence of a linear relationship (Fig. 2, $r = 0.997$, $\sigma = 0.01$, isokinetic temperature = 376 ± 9 K) between $\log k_2$ at 323 K and $\log k_2$ at 313 K indicates that a single mechanism is operating in all the solvent systems studied.

Fig. 2. The isokinetic plot for the unsubstituted aniline in all the mole fraction.

Solvent-reactivity correlation : The title reaction has been studied in thirteen different mole fractions of propan-2-ol in 2-methylpropan-2-ol. The second order rate constants collected in Table 1 increase with increase in mole fraction of propan-2-ol in the mixture. The rate data (Table 1) correlates satisfactorily with relative permittivity of the medium, ϵ_r , through Laidler-Eyring¹⁵ equation (Explained variance, $100r^2 > 90$) and also with Reichard's⁸ polarity parameters E_T^N ($100r^2 > 90$) and a representative plot is shown in Fig. 3. These bulk solvent properties will poorly describe the microenvironment around the reacting species, which governs the stability of the transition state and hence the rate of the reaction.

Therefore, in order to obtain a deeper insight into the various solvent-solvent-solute interactions, which influence reactivity, we have tried to adopt the solvatochromic comparison method developed by Kamlet and Taft¹⁶. The kinetic data were correlated with Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic parameters α , β and π^* in the form of the following Linear Solvation Energy Relationship (LSER).

$$\log k = A_0 + s\pi^* + a\alpha + b\beta \quad (2)$$

where, π^* = solvent dipolarity/polarizability, α = solvent hydrogen bond donor acidity (HBD) and β = solvent hydrogen bond acceptor basicity (HBA).

Fig. 3. The plot of $\log k_2$ versus E_T^N .

The regression coefficients s , a and b measure the relative susceptibilities of the solvent dependent solute property $\log k$ to the indicated solvent parameter. The rates of the reaction for all the compounds studied show a good correlation with solvent via the above LSER (eq. (2)) with an explained variance of *ca.* 95%. Such a good correlation indicates the existence of both specific and non-specific solute-solvent interactions in the present study.

From the values of the regression coefficients the contribution of each parameter, on a percentage basis, to reactivity were calculated and are listed in Table 4. The observation of this multiple regression analysis leads us to the following conclusions. (i) The positive sign of the coefficients of α and β terms suggest that the specific interaction, through H-bonding properties, between the transition state and the solvent is more than that between the reactants and the solvent. From (I) it is evident that the removal of chloride ion will be facilitated with increase in hydrogen bond donor property of the solvent. It is observed that, in the present study, increase in mole

Table 4. Statistical results and weighted percentage contributions for the correlation of $\log k_2$ with Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic parameters α , β and π^*

Substituent	$100R^2$	σ	a	b	s	P_α	P_β	P_{π^*}
H	95	0.03	0.87	-0.59	-3.96	16	11	73
<i>p</i> -Me	87	0.07	0.76	-0.32	-5.18	12	5	83
<i>p</i> -OMe	83	0.07	1.83	2.73	-4.95	19	29	52
<i>p</i> -COMe	99	0.01	0.82	0.90	0.74	33	37	30
<i>p</i> -NHCOMe	89	0.06	0.67	-0.42	-5.01	11	7	82
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	91	0.04	1.47	1.75	0.55	39	46	15
<i>p</i> -Cl	96	0.02	1.23	1.93	3.07	20	31	49
<i>p</i> -Br	97	0.02	1.38	2.46	2.20	23	41	36
<i>p</i> -F	93	0.04	1.26	1.40	-1.08	34	37	29
<i>m</i> -Me	88	0.06	1.21	0.23	1.45	42	8	50
<i>m</i> -OMe	94	0.02	0.53	0.07	-3.42	13	2	85
<i>m</i> -COMe	90	0.04	1.37	2.60	5.97	11	26	60
<i>m</i> -Et	91	0.08	0.67	-0.79	-5.49	10	11	79
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	95	0.02	0.93	1.47	-1.41	24	38	37

fraction of propan-2-ol in the mixture increases the rate of the reaction. This may be due to the fact that since propan-2-ol is a stronger HBD solvent, increase in its mole fraction in the mixture facilitates the chloride removal consequently enhancing the rate of the reaction. (ii) The solvent polarizability/dipolarity, as indicated by P_{π^*} , plays a dominant role in governing the reactivity. The sign of the coefficient of this term is randomly observed which suggests that the interaction is complex in nature.

Structure-reactivity correlation : The effect of substituents on the rate was studied with fourteen *para*- and *meta*-substituted anilines. The results in Table 1 reveal that in a given mole fraction, the rate constants vary with the nature of the substrate. The rate data correlate satisfactorily with pK_a values of anilines and also through Hammett equation. The statistical results and the reaction constant values in different mole fractions are given in Tables 5 and 6 and representative plots are given in Figs. 4 and 5. The Bronsted slope (β), which provide a measure of the sensitivity of the reaction to the basicity of the nucleophile¹⁷. The reaction constant, ρ , value for substituent variations on nucleophile is a measure of the degree of bond formation between nucleophile and substrate at the transition state. The results (Table 6) reveal that the ρ values are negative, implying that positive charge develops on the N-atom as the TS is formed. The

Table 5. Results of simple linear correlation of the rate constant with pK_a value in all the mole fraction of propan-2-ol investigated

Mole fraction of propan-2-ol	r	σ	β
1.0000	0.950	0.12	0.142 (0.03) ^a
0.9598	0.873	0.09	0.117 (0.02)
0.8770	0.902	0.07	0.097 (0.01)
0.7003	0.942	0.04	0.078 (0.01)
0.5572	0.946	0.04	0.081 (0.01)
0.4545	0.932	0.05	0.081 (0.01)
0.3490	0.935	0.05	0.088 (0.01)
0.1995	0.958	0.04	0.095 (0.01)
0.1485	0.971	0.03	0.095 (0.01)
0.1108	0.961	0.04	0.097 (0.01)
0.0696	0.935	0.04	0.080 (0.01)
0.0475	0.900	0.06	0.094 (0.01)
0.0243	0.912	0.07	0.109 (0.02)

^aValues in parentheses are standard errors.

magnitude of both ρ and β are low which suggest an easier bond cleavage in the TS¹⁷.

Multiple correlation analysis of the rate data through dual substituent parameter (DSP) equations^{18,19} reveals that the reactivity can be explained satisfactorily by F and R . In the case of *para*-substituted compounds, the correlation ($0.847 < r < 0.971$, $0.03 < \sigma < 0.08$, P_F ca. 65%, P_R ca. 35%) yields negative slope and with *meta*-substituted compounds ($0.845 < r < 0.977$, $0.02 < \sigma < 0.11$, P_F ca. 87%, P_R ca. 13%) also the slopes are negative. Similarly, σ_1 and σ_R^+ also correlates fairly

Table 6. Results of simple linear correlation of the rate constant with σ value in all the mole fraction of propan-2-ol investigated

Mole fraction of propan-2-ol	r	σ	ρ
1.0000	0.925	0.08	-0.629 (0.07) ^a
0.9598	0.941	0.06	-0.491 (0.05)
0.8770	0.905	0.06	-0.363 (0.05)
0.7003	0.935	0.04	-0.294 (0.03)
0.5572	0.945	0.03	-0.307 (0.03)
0.4545	0.905	0.04	-0.296 (0.04)
0.3490	0.927	0.04	-0.330 (0.04)
0.1995	0.958	0.03	-0.358 (0.03)
0.1485	0.982	0.02	-0.368 (0.02)
0.1108	0.981	0.02	-0.386 (0.02)
0.0696	0.963	0.03	-0.326 (0.02)
0.0475	0.909	0.09	-0.383 (0.05)
0.0243	0.925	0.06	-0.438 (0.05)

^aValues in parentheses are standard errors.

Fig. 4. The plot of $\log k_2$ versus pK_a .

with k_2 (*para*-substituted compound, $0.834 < r < 0.986$, $0.02 < \sigma < 0.10$, P_I ca. 46%, P_R ca. 54%) (*meta*-substituted compound, $0.814 < r < 0.974$, $0.02 < \sigma < 0.12$, P_I ca. 78%, P_R ca. 22%). In both the correlations, the *meta*-compounds show the predominant inductive effect as expected.

The rate constants were analyzed in terms of LDR equation (eq. (3)) introduced by Charton²⁰ for the quantitative description of structural effects on chemical reactivities.

$$\log k = L\sigma_1 + D\sigma_d + R\sigma_e + h \quad (3)$$

where, σ_1 is a localized (field and/or inductive) effect parameter, σ_d is the intrinsic delocalized (resonance) electrical effect parameter when active site electronic demand is minimal and σ_e represents the sensitivity of the substituent to change in electronic demand by the active site. L , D and R are the coefficients of the σ_1 , σ_d and σ_e parameters respectively. The triparametric model results from the fact that substituent types differ in their mode of electron delocalization. This difference is reflected in a different sensitivity to the electronic demand of the phenomenon being studied. The latter two substituent parameters are related as :

$$\sigma_D = \eta\sigma_e + \sigma_d \quad (4)$$

where η represents the electronic demand of the reaction site which is given by $\eta = R/D$, and σ_D represents the delocalized electrical parameter of the diparametric LD equation which varies with the magnitude and sign of η .

Fig. 5. The plot of $\log k_2$ versus σ .

The rates of the reaction of the *para*-substituted anilines showed a good correlation with LDR equation and the statistical parameters are collected in Table 7. Due to lack of the minimum required number of data points, to correlate with LDR equation, the *meta*-substituents are not included. The comparison of the L and D values for the substituted anilines showed that the reaction of *para*-substituted anilines is more susceptible to the delocalised effect than the localized effect. All the regression coefficients, L , D and R are negative indicating an electron-deficient reaction center in the transition state of the

Table 7. Results of the correlation analysis of the rate data of anilines-benzenesulphonyl chloride reaction with *LDR* parameters

Mole fraction of propan-2-ol	<i>L</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>R</i>	η	R^2	σ	P_D
1.0000	-0.639 (0.16) ^a	-0.546 (0.15)	-0.531 (0.89)	0.97	0.952	0.10	46
0.9598	-0.532 (0.13)	-0.433 (0.11)	-0.149 (0.69)	0.34	0.966	0.08	45
0.8770	-0.334 (0.11)	-0.307 (0.10)	-0.327 (0.62)	1.06	0.904	0.07	48
0.7003	-0.263 (0.05)	-0.210 (0.05)	-0.705 (0.31)	3.35	0.919	0.04	44
0.5572	-0.249 (0.07)	-0.284 (0.06)	-0.356 (0.39)	1.26	0.986	0.05	53
0.4545	-0.259 (0.07)	-0.293 (0.06)	-0.276 (0.38)	0.94	0.900	0.04	53
0.3490	-0.298 (0.09)	-0.374 (0.08)	-0.084 (0.50)	0.23	0.968	0.06	56
0.1995	-0.334 (0.08)	-0.375 (0.07)	-0.036 (0.43)	0.10	0.904	0.05	53
0.1485	-0.365 (0.06)	-0.361 (0.05)	-0.057 (0.32)	0.16	0.947	0.04	50
0.1108	-0.398 (0.04)	-0.353 (0.04)	-0.124 (0.22)	0.35	0.975	0.03	47
0.0696	-0.379 (0.05)	-0.267 (0.05)	-0.019 (0.29)	0.07	0.944	0.03	41
0.0475	-0.534 (0.05)	-0.297 (0.04)	-0.082 (0.27)	0.27	0.970	0.03	36
0.0243	-0.584 (0.04)	-0.352 (0.04)	-0.102 (0.24)	0.29	0.981	0.03	38

^aValues in parentheses are standard errors.

reaction. The positive value of η adds a negative increment to σ_d (eq. (4)), increasing the donor effect of the substituent where σ_d is negative and decreasing the acceptor effect where σ_d is positive. The substituent is therefore better able to stabilize a cationic or electronically deficient reaction site. This also supports the presence of an electron-deficient center in the transition state of the rate-determining step. This observation supports the nature of the transition state as given (I). The percent contribution of the delocalized effect, P_D is given by the following equation.

$$P_D = (|D| \times 100) / (|L| + |D|) \quad (5)$$

The value of P_D is also recorded in Table 7. The value of P_D for the reaction of *para*-substituted aniline is dominant, ca. 58%, as mentioned above.

Conclusion : The results of the correlation of rate data with Hammett equation and with *LDR* equation suggest an electron-deficient reaction center in the transition state of the reaction. The correlation of the reaction rates with solvent parameters via Kamlet-Taft equation indicates the existence of both specific and non-specific solute-solvent interactions in the present study. Further the dipolarity/polarizability of the solvent plays a major role in governing the reactivity and the rate of the reaction was found to increase with increase in polarity of the medium. The formation of a transition state as depicted in (I) is well supported by the results of solvent and structural effects.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (DSB) is highly thankful the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for providing financial assistance in the form of SRF.

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